

Article

An Introduction to Sociology of Science and Technology

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Tapas Roy*

Growing interest to study Science and Technology started to emerge as an interdisciplinary field of study during the 1970s, under the umbrella term science and technology studies (STS). The same analytical frameworks started to use in the studies of science and technology. The following gives a brief overview of the important trajectories of the development of sociological interest in studying technology since the rise of science and Technology studies, how sociology started to view technology, and the major theoretical approaches with some sample works.

Keywords: Strong Program, STS, SCOT, ANT, Interpretative flexibility, EPOR, Symmetry

Introduction

The sociology of science and technology was not alien to sociology, but the decade of 1970s can be marked by the growing momentum in the field of science and technology studies. The newly emerged interdisciplinary field of studies namely Science Technology and Society started to grow their interest in studying science and technology from a newly emerging perspective in philosophy, sociology, and history. The following literature review offers an understanding of the intellectual structure of the sociology of science and Sociology of technology, its legacy, evolution, major propositions, and major contributors.

- The Author is a PhD scholar, Department of Sociology, The University of Burdwan

To get an understanding of science and technology studies it is essential to historically review the works of the sociologist who paid attention to the studies of science and technology and how their legacy continues to influence the study of today's science and technology study. Early insight into the sociology of science can be found in Max Weber's essay *Science as Vocation* in 1917. Weber explores the nature and significance of science in modern society and reflects on the motivations and challenges faced by individuals who pursue scientific careers. Sociology of science was pursued since the 1930s by Robert K. Merton but did not draw the attraction of other sociologists. At the same time, William Ogburn brought forward the notion of technological determinism in 1922. "Ogburn posited four stages of technical development: invention, accumulation, diffusion, and adjustment. Invention is the process by which new forms of technology are created. Inventions are collective contributions to an existing cultural base that cannot occur unless the society has already gained a certain level of knowledge and expertise in the particular area. Accumulation is the growth of technology because new things are invented more rapidly than old ones are forgotten, and some inventions (such as writing) promote this accumulation process. Diffusion is the spread of an idea from one cultural group to another, or from one field of activity to another, and as diffusion brings inventions together, they combine to form new inventions. Adjustment is the process by which the non-technical aspects of a culture respond to the invention, and any retardation of this adjustment process causes cultural lag." (Wikipedia)

In 1938 Robert K Merton published his thesis *Science, Technology, and Society in Seventeenth-Century England*- The book examines the social, cultural, and intellectual context of scientific and technological developments in England during the seventeenth century. Inspired by Max Weber's work on *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of*

Capitalism (1905), he examined the rise and development of science in England associated with Puritan ethics. He raised important issues on the connections between religion and the rise of modern science, became a significant work in the realm of the sociology of science, and continues to be cited in new scholarship.

In *The Neglect of the Sociology of Science* (1952), Robert K. Merton; "among current introductory textbooks in sociology ... all deal at length with the institutions of family, state, and economy, many with the institution of religion, but very few indeed with science as a major institution in modern society." (Merton, 1952-P 211) Sociologists never paid serious sociological attention to the understanding of science and technology partly because philosophers didn't or sociology was still evolving. After two successive world wars which involved the intensive use of modern technology started to draw the attention of the philosophers. In the decades after the Second World War, Martin Heidegger's writings on modernity came to focus explicitly on the problem of technology. Although only two essays *The Question Concerning Technology and Other Essays* (1954) are explicitly devoted to it, technology is a primary issue in all of Heidegger's work subsequent to 1930. In ordinary German, Technik means both technology and technique, yet Heidegger does not see technology in this conventional manner. Rather, for Heidegger, 'Technology is a way of revealing.' Essentially, then, technology is not about machines, complex techniques, or the manufacture of artifacts in Heidegger's conception. The essence of technology is itself not technological. As Heidegger sums it up: 'Our age is not a technological age because it is the age of the machine; it is the age of the machine because it is the technological age. (Heidegger, M, 1954) In Heidegger's ontological perspective, technology is neither neutral nor instrumental. It signifies a particular mode of disclosure. It reveals Being in a particular way.

In 1962 Thomas Khun published *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, he examined the difference between normal science and revolutionary science; by normal science, he referred to the periods of conceptual continuity where there is cumulative progress occurs, "interrupted by periods of revolutionary science. The discovery of "anomalies" during revolutions in science leads to new paradigms." (Wikipedia) He refers to this as the paradigmatic shift.

The 1970s the decade can be marked by growing momentum for the development and formalization of the sub-disciplinary field of studies in sociology in association with other allied disciplines of social sciences like history, and philosophy. The publication of *The Structure of Scientific Revolution* 1962 by Thomas Khun drew the attention of philosophers, sociologists, and historians to the understanding of science from their own respected fields and perspectives. An early breakthrough was achieved with the formation of Science and Technology Studies (STS) which was an Interdisciplinary branch of studies of social science. STS was constituted by history, philosophy, and sociology of science and technology." An origin story could identify such key moments in the birth process of this field as the first publication of *Science Studies* (later *Social Studies of Science*) in Edinburgh in 1971. the founding of the Society for Social Studies of Science in 1975, and the historic first meeting of the society at Cornell University in 1976." (Bauchspies et al., 2006)

A volume of Merton's essays from the 1930s through 1960s on the sociology of science appeared in 1971, *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*; the goal of the sociology of science is to examine the linkage between science and social structure using the "conceptual frameworks" of sociology. The sociology of science needs to be based on empirical observation -- i.e., it cannot be a purely conceptual discipline. But it must possess an appropriate framework of

sociological theory within the context of which empirical observations of scientific practice can be explained (Little, 2009).

- One of Merton's key methodological contributions was the idea that it was possible to observe and measure the institutions of science through careful empirical examination of the biographies, journals, and other objective markers of scientific activity.
- Another of Merton's key ideas is the role of the reward system of science, which he takes to be the motor of scientific change.
- And he finds that this reward system gives great weight to originality and priority -- which leads to the recurring phenomena of priority disputes, fraud, and plagiarism in science.
- A final topic of interest in Merton's sociology of science is his treatment of "peer review". Here is how he describes this part of the institutions of science in "Institutionalized Patterns of Evaluation in Science" (Little, 2009)

In 1973 Merton wrote *The Normative Structure of Science* in his revised edition of *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*. The normative structure of science also known as "the scientific ethos" often abbreviated as CUDOS, refers to the set of norms and values that guide scientific practice. These include the values of universalism (the idea that scientific knowledge is valid regardless of the identity of the scientist producing it), communism (the idea that scientific knowledge should be shared freely and openly), disinterestedness (the idea that scientific research should be pursued for its own sake rather than for personal gain), and organized skepticism (the idea that scientific claims should be subjected to rigorous scrutiny and testing).

One of Merton's key contributions to the sociology of science is his concept of "the scientific ethos," which refers to the set of

norms and values that guide the conduct of scientific research. According to Merton, these norms include a commitment to objectivity, scepticism, and the pursuit of knowledge for its own sake, rather than for personal or political gain. Merton also developed the concept of the "Matthew Effect" in science, which refers to the tendency for successful scientists to receive greater recognition and resources than less successful scientists, creating a self-reinforcing cycle of success and recognition.

The Strong Programme and the Sociology of Scientific Knowledge (SSK)

The strong programme or strong sociology is a variety of the sociology of scientific knowledge (SSK) particularly associated with David Bloor, Barry Barnes, Harry Collins, Donald A. MacKenzie. The Strong Program is a programmatic statement that calls upon social scientists to examine the social content and underpinnings of scientific knowledge. It played an important part in the wider development of the field of sociology of scientific knowledge. The Strong Program originated from the so-called Edinburgh school in the mid-1970s and was most famously set out by David Bloor in his 1976 book, *Knowledge and Social Imagery*. (Eriksson, 2007). The strong programme has four indispensable components formulated by David Bloor:

- Causality: it examines the conditions (psychological, social, and cultural) that bring about claims to a certain kind of knowledge.
- Impartiality: it examines successful as well as unsuccessful knowledge claims.
- Symmetry: the same types of explanations are used for successful and unsuccessful knowledge claims alike.
- Reflexivity: it must be applicable to sociology itself.

How we investigate and think about science in ways that move us beyond the 'traditional' or

'common sense' understandings. We will look at The Strong Programme, which is considered to be one of the foundational influences on the sociology of science. In particular, we will look at its principle of symmetry and how it helped us begin to understand the work that goes into making scientific knowledge, and how vital the 'social' is in this process. We will also consider some of the critiques of the Strong Programme and how it may or may not be useful today.

Empirical Programme of Relativism (EPOR)

Harry Collins's project in the sociology of knowledge – the Empirical Programme of Relativism (EPOR) – is inspired by the Strong Programme. However, Collins rejects the idea that explanation should be causal, and eschews explanation of the genesis of theories: only their reception can be accounted for. EPOR is divided into three stages: (1) Demonstrating the "*interpretative flexibility*" of experimental data. (2) Showing the local social mechanisms by which *closure* is affected. (3) Linking the local closure mechanisms to wider social forces.

Because the strong programme originated at the 'Science Studies Unit,' University of Edinburgh, it is sometimes termed the Edinburgh School. However, there is also a Bath School associated with Harry Collins that makes similar proposals. In contrast to the Edinburgh School, which emphasizes historical approaches, the Bath School emphasizes microsocial studies of laboratories and experiments. The Bath school, however, does depart from the strong programme on some fundamental issues. In the social construction of technology (SCOT) approach developed by Collins' student Trevor Pinch, as well as by the Dutch sociologist Wiebe Bijker, the strong programme was extended to technology. There are SSK-influenced scholars working in science and technology studies programs throughout the world (Douglas, 2012).

Science and Technology Studies (STS)

In 1979, Bruno Latour and Steve Woolgar published *Laboratory Life*; their work "concerns the way in which the daily activities of working scientists lead to the construction of scientific facts (Latour & Woolgar, 1979)". The book is considered to be one of the most influential works in the laboratory studies tradition within Science and Technology Studies. The book was an ethnomethodological study of a scientific laboratory and its purpose was to document the creation of scientific facts in the laboratories. "Using a variety of techniques from anthropology, semiotics, and biological fact. In the context of lab work. They concentrate on a process they called "deletion of modalities." a progressive stripping away of contextual information about the production, with the end result being a fact bare of biographical. *Laboratory Life*, therefore, stands in opposition to the study of scandalous moments in which the so-called "normal" operation of science was disrupted by external forces. In contrast, Latour and Woolgar give an account of how scientific facts are produced in a laboratory in situ (on-site), or as it happens.

From Laboratory Life to Actor Network Theory

The 'strong programme' argued that broad social and political conditions could influence the content of scientific knowledge. Towards the end of the 1970s sociology of science took a distinctly micro-social (and linguistic) turn. Detailed studies of scientists, in laboratories or making claims in papers, became the preferred methodology of 'lab anthropologists. The complex negotiations, contingencies and skills involved in creating 'a fact' (and the way that these were all erased from the final product) became the focus of attention. The *Laboratory Life* developed an important analytical framework. It is inspired by but not entirely dependent on the ethnomethodological approach. In turn, it served as the inspiration for Actor-network

theory (or ANT); many of ANT's core concepts (like transcription, inscription, translation, and the deployment of networks) are present in Laboratory Life. One of the most influential schools of thought since the 1980s and 1990s has been 'actor network theory' (ANT). Its central idea is that 'facts' are created when 'heterogeneous' assemblages of actors and objects are mobilized into a 'network'. Science and society are both co-created as the laboratory is used as a focal point for assembling knowledge and redefining social interests. Science becomes 'politics by other means'.

The Technological Turn

The Turn to Technology in Social Studies of Science refers to the increasing interest and use of technology in studying science as a social practice. This approach recognizes that science is not simply a set of objective facts and theories, but a complex social and cultural phenomenon that is shaped by the values, beliefs, and practices of scientists and society at large.

One way that technology has been used in social studies of science is through the analysis of digital data. With the proliferation of digital platforms and tools, scientists are generating vast amounts of data that can be analyzed to better understand the scientific process and its social implications. This includes analyzing online discussions among scientists, tracking the spread of scientific ideas through social media, and using machine learning algorithms to identify patterns in scientific publications.

Another way that technology has been used is through the development of new tools and methods for studying science. For example, virtual reality has been used to simulate scientific experiments, allowing researchers to better understand the cognitive processes involved in scientific reasoning. Similarly, computer simulations have been

used to model complex scientific phenomena, such as climate change, and to explore different scenarios and potential outcomes.

Overall, the turn to technology in social studies of science reflects a growing recognition that science is a complex and dynamic social practice that cannot be fully understood without taking into account the role of technology in shaping scientific knowledge and practice.

In 1984 Trevor J. Pinch; Wiebe E. Bijker published *The Social Construction of Facts and Artefacts: or How the Sociology of Science and the Sociology of Technology might Benefit Each Other*. They argue that the ways a technology is used cannot be understood without understanding how that technology is embedded in its social context. SCOT can be understood as the rejection of the classical idea of technological determinism and is sometimes known as technological constructivism. SCOT draws on work done in the constructivist school of the sociology of scientific knowledge, and its subtopics include actor-network theory (a branch of the sociology of science and technology) and historical analysis of sociotechnical systems, such as the work of historian Thomas P. Hughes. Its empirical methods are an adaptation of the Empirical Programme of Relativism (EPOR), which outlines a method of analysis to demonstrate the ways in which scientific findings are socially constructed (see strong program). Leading adherents of SCOT include Wiebe Bijker and Trevor Pinch.

In his article "The turn to technology in social studies of science," 1994 Steve Woolgar argues that the increasing reliance on technology in scientific research has led to a corresponding turn towards studying the social aspects of technology in the field of Science and Technology Studies (STS).

Woolgar asserts that the traditional focus of STS on the social construction of scientific knowledge needs to be complemented by an examination of the

material practices involved in scientific research, particularly the role of technological tools and instruments. He argues that these tools are not simply neutral objects used by scientists to produce knowledge but are themselves shaped by social and cultural factors.

“Theoretical significance of the sociology of scientific knowledge (SSK) is affected by attempts to apply relativist-constructivism to technology. The article shows that the failure to confront key analytic ambivalences in the practice of SSK has compromised its original strategic significance. In particular, the construal of SSK as an explanatory formula diminishes its potential for profoundly reconceptualizing epistemic issues. A consideration of critiques of technological determinism, and of some empirical studies, reveals similar analytic ambivalences in the social study of technology (SST). The injunction to consider “technology as text” is critically examined. It is concluded that a reflexive interpretation of this slogan is necessary to recover some of the epistemological significance lost in the constructivist move from SSK to SST(Woolgar, 1991). “

SCOT holds that those who seek to understand the reasons for acceptance or rejection of a technology should look to the social world. It is not enough, according to SCOT, to explain a technology's success by saying that it is “the best”—researchers must look at how the criteria of being “the best” is defined and what groups and stakeholders participate in defining it. They must ask who defines the technical criteria success is measured by, why technical criteria are defined this way, and who is included or excluded. Pinch and Bijker argue that technological determinism is a myth that results when one looks backward and believes that the path

taken to the present was the only possible path. SCOT is not only a theory, but also a methodology: it formalizes the steps and principles to follow when one wants to analyze the causes of technological failures or successes.

In 1986 Langdon Winner, a *political theorist and philosopher* "**The Whale and the Reactor: A Search for Limits in an Age of High Technology**" Winner argues that technology is not a neutral tool or instrument, but a product of political and social values, and as such, it shapes and is shaped by society. Winner uses the metaphor of a whale and a reactor to represent two different perspectives on technology. The whale represents a holistic view of technology, where technology is seen as part of a larger social and natural ecosystem. The reactor, on the other hand, represents a reductionist view of technology, where technology is seen as an isolated and autonomous entity.

Winner explores various case studies, such as the development of the nuclear reactor and the design of urban highways, to illustrate how technology can have significant social and political consequences. He argues that we need to be aware of the values and assumptions that underlie technological development and use, and that we need to engage in more democratic and participatory decision-making processes to ensure that technology serves the common good. Overall, "The Whale and the Reactor" offers a critical perspective on the relationship between technology and society and raises important questions about the role of technology in shaping our lives and our world.

Conclusion

On summing up, Sociology of technology is being shaped by the same analytical framework of study employed in sociology of science and sociology of knowledge. It is exploring the social dimension of technology. Contemporary studies on how Military and Security Technologies examine the sociology of

technology by focussing in on a generic class of technologies related to the military and security. The aim is to provide an overview of how diverse STS perspectives have approached the question of where military technologies come from and how they have been shaped by broader social, political and economic factors.

Chronology

1. Merton, RK (1952) *The Neglect of the Sociology of Science*
2. Martin Heidegger (1954) *The Question Concerning Technology*
3. Khun T (1962) *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*
4. Berger, P and Luckman, T (1966), *The social construction of reality: a treatise in the sociology of knowledge*
5. Merton, RK (1971) *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*
6. Merton, RK (1973), 'The Normative Structure of Science', in *The Sociology of Science* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press), Chapter 13 pp267-278
7. Bloor, D (1976), *Knowledge and Social Imagery* (Routledge) esp. Chapter 1 'The Strong Programme in the Sociology of Knowledge, 3-23
8. Winner, Langdon. 1980. "Do artifacts have Politics? *Daedalus*, 109: 121-36.
9. Latour, B and Woolgar, S (1986) [1976] "An Anthropologist visits the Laboratory", in *Laboratory Life: The Construction of Scientific Facts*, N.J; Chichester: Princeton University Press: 43-88. [e-book available from UCL library; the chapter also on the e-reading list on Moodle site]
10. Bloor, D (1981), 'The Strengths of the Strong Programme', *Philosophy of the Social Sciences*, Vol.11(2) pp.199-213.
11. Trevor J. Pinch; Wiebe E. Bijker (1984) *The Social Construction of Facts and Artefacts: or How the Sociology of Science and the Sociology of Technology might Benefit Each Other*. *Social Studies of Science* 14 (3) 399-441.
12. Latour, B. and Woolgar, S. (1986) *Laboratory Life: The Construction of Scientific Facts*. Chapter 1 'From order to disorder' (pp. 15-42). Electronic copy available through UCL Library Catalogue
13. Latour, B (1987), *Science in Action* (Harvard University Press) (especially introduction and chapters 1 & 2) (A classic overview of Latour's theories) (Chapter 2 'Laboratories' is on Moodle e-reading list)

References

Bauchspies, W. K., Croissant, J., & Restivo, S. P. (2006). *Science, technology, and society: A sociological approach*. Blackwell Pub.

Douglas, D. G. (2012). *The Social Construction of Technological Systems*. The MIT Press; JSTOR. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt5vjrsq>

Eriksson, L. (2007). Strong Program. In G. Ritzer (Ed.), *The Blackwell Encyclopedia of Sociology* (p. wbeoss287). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405165518.wbeoss287>

Latour, B., & Woolgar, S. (1979). *Laboratory life: The social construction of scientific facts*. Sage Publications.

Little, D. (2009, December 17). Understanding Society: Merton's sociology of science. *Understanding Society*. <https://understandingsociety.blogspot.com/2009/12/mertons-sociology-of-science.html>

Woolgar, S. (1991). The Turn to Technology in Social Studies of Science. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 16(1), 20–50. JSTOR.